

Supplementary information

A global expert assessment on the role of beehive acoustic-based honeybee (*Apis* spp.) (Apidae; Hymenoptera) colony monitoring

Supplementary figures regarding personal information of experts/researchers:

Figure 1: Participation of each gender (%) to respond to the questionnaire.

Figure 2: Age of participants who have given their responses to the questionnaire.

Figure 3: Level of education of the experts who provided their feedback via a questionnaire.

Figure 4: Employment status of the experts who participated to respond the questionnaire.